

HISTORICAL AND COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF ZONYMS IN THE UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

The processes taking place in the considered equinymic sublanguage, its development, and formation in the comparative-typological aspect in the Russian and Uzbek languages have not yet become the object of a special study for domestic and foreign linguists.

Zonyms, as functional-semantic groups of lexical units, rarely became the object of comparative study; due to their linguistic specificity, they provide rich and interesting material for studying the problem of reflecting the picture of the world in language.

Insufficient theoretical knowledge of the microsystem of zonymy - equinymy, as structural and semantic sign formations relevant for native speakers, coupled with the applied significance of zoosemia problems for Turkology and the Russian language, serve as a justification for the need for this article.

Vocabulary, the vocabulary of a language is a set of numerous interrelated semantic microstructures, which include synonymy, homonymy, polysemy, and antonymy of the lexical plan. The range of these semantic microstructures is expanding due to other meaningful phenomena, one of them being the so-called equinymy.

So, equines are words of the same level of generalization with a common hypernym - the name of the concept of a generic character. Equonym - a concept and a name that expresses it in relation to other concepts and names of the same level of generalization in a non-hierarchical system. For example, in the system of concepts "mother", "father", and "parent", the concept and the word "mother" is equity in relation to the word "father" and a hyponym in relation to the word "parent". In turn, "parent" is a hypernym in relation to the words "mother" and "father". This leads to the conclusion that equinymy is a relation that connects concepts and equiname words.

Equonymy, as one of the most important varieties of systematic microsystems in the dictionary of the functional-semantic plan, is on the same level as the phenomena of paronymy; Equonymic relation is similar to patronymic relation. In the

paradigmatics of paronymy and equinymy, there are common features. In the paradigmatic series of paronymy and equinymy, one of the members is dominant in relation to the other member. The semantic relations between the lexemes человек (odam), голова (bosh), тело (tana), рука (qo'l), нога (oyoq) are carried out with the help of a paronymic relationship, where the человек (odam) is the dominant member, and the rest are dependent members of this paradigm. A similar paradigm consists of semantic relations of lexemes such as horse (ot), foal (toy), where the dominant member of the paradigm is the lexeme horse (ot), and the others are its dependent members. Here, between the members of this paradigm, equinymic relations are presented. Paronyms and paronymic relations, equinames and equionymic relations are phenomena of a different nature. The difference between these phenomena is characterized by the fact that the semantic connection between the members of the paronymic series is isolated; dependent members of the paronymic paradigm are not semantically related to their dominant member - the человек (odam), голова (bosh), тело (tana), рука (qo'l), нога (oyoq) individually do not mean "man" as a whole. In equinomic relations, the opposite is true: each dependent member is semantically equal to the dominant member of the paradigmatic series. So, for example, the lexeme pig is the dominant member of the equinomic series in relation to its dependent members - boar, sow, piglet. However, a boar is also a pig, a sow is also a pig, a piglet is also. This indicates that between the dominant and dependent members of the equionymic paradigm, a

functional-semantic community is found, and not isolation, which cannot be said about the relationship between the dominant and dependent members of the paronymic paradigm.

The system of zoonyms is widely used in speech. On the basis of the names of the system of zoonyms, the names of anthroponymic, toponymic, hydronymic characters are formed, which is widespread in the Uzbek and Russian languages, and the languages of other peoples.

The names of zoonyms are also used in the formation of professional terms, a striking example of which is the naming system of Tajik jewelry and embroidery terminology (tovus, murg'ob / murg'obi, to'ti, ajdarho, kabutar, govzar, sag'zan, etc.).

Thus, for equinames, the system of domestic, wild animals and the system of names of some birds is the richest. Equonyms are also words (lexemes). As a word, they are at the center of the lexical system of the language. The word is the basic and central unit of the language and constitutes the systemic structure of the entire vocabulary. The equinymic nature of individual words is characterized by the fact that they constitute one of the varieties of mediostructure in relation to another systemic structure of the lexical composition - microstructure and macrostructure.

The relationship of equinames to the concept of mediostructure of the general system of a lexeme is explained by the nature of the internal organization of various lexico-semantic groups, united by paradigmatic-associative links between their members, which are represented by the presence of numerous functional-

semantic microsystems with a common meaning of individual zoonyms.

As mentioned above, equinymy (and equinymy) are organically related to the concepts of hypernyms (and hypernyms), which have generic meanings of concepts. The semantic plan of hypernyms is wide-ranging. This is explained by the fact that the process of neutralization of its individual distinctive semantic structure takes place in it. Under the influence of neutralization, the opposite members of the paradigmatic series of hyperonyms differ from each other. Each generic name with the general meaning of a certain zoonym is used as part of certain functional-semantic microsystems with the meanings "sheep", "goat", "donkey", "mule", "pig", etc.

A characteristic feature of zoonyms in the Russian and Uzbek languages is a high degree of idiomaticity with a high content of nominativeness. This leads to the fact that zoonyms similar in denotative meanings in these two languages differ in figurativeness, since associative ideas about animals in different languages do not coincide. So, in the Russian language the word behemoth has a metaphorical rethinking, and in the Uzbek language the word медведь "ayiq," has a rethinking of this nature. Both of them are used in relation to a clumsy, fat person, etc.

As the analysis of the lexical material showed, the main word-forming part of the zoonyms of the Russian and Uzbek languages is their root part, which goes back to ancient times with its etymology. A number of word-forming formants in zoonyms of the Uzbek language are borrowed from the Indo-European, and in particular, from the Persian-Tadjik languages. Another group of word-forming

parts of zoonyms of the Uzbek language corresponds to zoonymic words in many Turkish languages.

In addition, we can define the distinctive features of hyperonymy and equinymy of the Russian and Uzbek languages using examples of zoonymic vocabulary (pets and birds).

So, we have found that the semantic plan of hypernyms is wide in volume, compared with the semantic plan of equinames, therefore, within the framework of the semantic plan of hypernyms, the meanings of two or more independent words are combined that function as equinames in relation to the corresponding (certain) hypernym. The wide-ranging nature of the semantic plan of hypernyms is explained by the fact that they neutralize individual distinguishing senses according to the signs of natural gender and degree of age, which act as the main, dominant sense meanings of their equinames, semantically dependent on individual hypernym lexemes. So, for example, in the semantic structure of the lexeme horse, as a hypernym word, the meanings of the lexemes mare, foal, dependent on it, are syncretically combined. In the semantic structure of the lexeme, the horse plays an important role in the phenomenon of neutralization, which is carried out according to two distinguishing features: according to the sign of the natural gender "male - female" (stallion - mare) and according to the sign of the degree of age (stallion - foal; mare - foal).

Based on the theoretical generalization of the information received, we can say that the influence of extralinguistic factors contributed to the formation and development of hyponymic and equinymic

relationships for both Russian zoonyms and Uzbek zoonyms.

We can conclude that without exception, all zoonyms with the representative meaning "pet" have a developed polysemantic microsystem, figurative meanings that form a human-meaning metaphor. The number of root words denoting wild animals is, in principle, very large; only an insignificant part is distinguished in them,

which has a detailed figurative meaning. This is due not to linguistic reasons, but to external (extralinguistic) ones: the closest contact of a person with the environment, with its representatives from the animal world, determines the semantic content of precisely those words that nominate the varieties closest to a person. Therefore, in this study, we mainly dealt with domestic animals and birds.

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